

8 Theory - The Axis of Evil

O Manor

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Abstract:

In this paper, an analysis of the Axis of evil will be made as part of a Lorentz manifold, (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$. The manifold is a connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary. The analysis will be made based on the coupling constant equation and the main equation of the framework, describing large-scale behavior of the manifold overtime. The reasoning behind the "Axis of Evil" is the existence of the topological space, which is a unique space, invariant to all positions in the matrix.

Introduction

The main equations in our new framework:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad - \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

Describing the Lorentz manifold (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times R$. Equation (1.1) satisfy the Einstein principle of equivalence and expends it to a cause and effect relationship. Invoking a stationary manifold, any amount of curvature on it, will yield an outward acceleration of the matrix. In that sense, it is different from general relativity, as there is no need to insert the cosmological constant as a separate entity. Using that equation, we built a new way to explain relativity by saying that two distinct observers will cause different accelerations of the matrix, and so, by measuring the same object, will reach different times and distances. The second equation of the 8-theory framework:

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.21)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

In our theory, the manifold has a varying metric according to a varying topology. The subtle idea is that the manifold has a compact topological space that is accessible from every point given high enough energy. Such space covers every point in metric space. Such a space is what makes the theory work, it is the space keeping the manifold stationary and with the second condition causing it to accelerate outward. Since there are no coordinates to such space, it is the same everywhere, and since every point in the metric is connected to it, there could be the illusion that each point in space was the point in which something cosmologically significant has accrued at singularity.

Not the whole topological space is satisfying the condition, $\partial g / \partial t = 0$ there are arbitrary variations in that space which vanish into matter on the metric, we have proved it in previous papers. Each net variation that is isomorphic to the prime numbers or to the number one, and thus we were able to prove the coupling constant series, presented in equation (2) and (2.1). The point of this short essay is the fact that there is an underlying space, which is invariant to metric coordinate and covers the entire metric. We know it covers the entire metric as the manifold is connected to the topological space but no spatial coordinates are given in equation (1.1).

The topological space is then invariant, and the equation is really a right to left chain of the order. Notice that the chain (3) is exactly describing the order in which things are happening in cosmological scales.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \leftarrow \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \leftarrow \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \leftarrow \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \quad (3)$$

It is very hard to reason for a compact topological space, as they are so different from the metric spaces. One did the best of his ability; there could be a better and simpler way to explain it. Time will tell.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)